

Publication Pattern of Scientists of CSIR National Institute for Interdisciplinary Science and Technology (NIIST), Thiruvananthapuram: A Scientometric Study

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Abstract

In this paper an attempt has been made to highlight quantitative growth and development of the CSIR- National Institute of Interdisciplinary Science & Technology (NIIST), Thiruvananthapuram in terms of publication output for the years 2007-2011. During the period, a total of 1080 publications and 110 patents were published. The average number of publications per year was 216. The highest numbers of papers (242) were published in 2008 and 41 patents awarded in the same year. Authorship and collaboration trend were towards multi-authored paper and the degree of collaboration was 0.986. There were 1066 (99%) multi-authored/collaborative papers and only 14(1%) single authored publications. The most preferred journals for publication by the scientists were: Journal of Alloys and Compounds, Journal of the American Ceramic Society and Bio resource Technology.

Keywords: Authorship Pattern, Co-Authorship Index, Degree of Collaboration, Kerala, National Institute for Interdisciplinary Science and Technology, Scientometrics, Thiruvananthapuram

1. Introduction

In most developed countries, the evaluation of the quality and quantity of basic research has been prevalent for decades. Science and scientific communication are so interrelated that one influences the other for the generation of information. It is widely accepted that public research performed in academic and governmental research institutions is a driving force behind the technology and economic growth. With the governments' funding research institutions and their libraries abundantly, it also becomes of paramount interest for the funding agencies and the research institutions to understand the performance so as to channelize the funds and manage them effectively.

Nowadays bibliometrics/ scientometrics is increasingly being used as a tool for a critical assessment of research output of countries, specific subject disciplines as well as academic and research institutes. This is evident from the fact that bibliometrics/scientometrics has been promoted as a separate discipline under Library and Information Science (LIS). Bibliometrics is an academic discipline and much research is being carried out for a quantitative study of the various aspects of literature of a given subject. Bibliometric techniques are now being vigorously pursued and with the result, it has been found that one-fourth of all the articles published in LIS literature are on bibliometrics/ scientometrics and its related topics. The quantifying methods employed in a bibliometric study yield a

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fairly good idea about an institute's contribution in the national scientific output.

Bibliometric studies have been conducted by different authors for studying research output, publication trend, author collaboration, citation impact and other bibliometric indicators and few studies were based on CSIR research and development institutions. In this paper, an attempt has been made to describe the growth and impact of research contributions, channels of communication, collaboration and authorship pattern of research carried out by the scientists at NIIST during the period 2007-2011.

2. National Institute of Interdisciplinary Science and Technology

National Institute of Interdisciplinary Science & Technology (NIIST) started functioning as a constituent laboratory of the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) in Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala. Initially established in 1975 as a CSIR Complex, it was named as the Regional Research Laboratory (RRL) in 1978 and later renamed as NIIST in 2007. Its mandate is to conduct research and development activities of the highest quality in areas related to effective utilization of resources of the region and of fundamental importance to the country. Currently NIIST is engaged in R & D programmes in areas related to Agro processing, Chemical Sciences, Materials Science and Technology, Biotechnology, Process Engineering and Environmental Technology¹.

During the three decades of its existence, the laboratory has witnessed phenomenal growth with addition of state-of-art infrastructure, technological up-gradation of the R&D facilities coupled with quantum jump in the output. In a recent analysis by CSIR-NISCAIR, the Institute achieved the second position among the CSIR labs in terms of number of high impact factor publications (890 numbers with average IF more than two per paper), 79 US patents filed and more than Rs. 48 crores received as ECF, during 2004–2008².

The institute has established state-of-the-art facilities for conducting advanced research in the areas of its interest. Pilot plant facilities for research training and process/product development in the areas of spices and oilseeds have been established. The institute has also been playing a significant role in human resource development by training post graduate/graduate students, with over 252

Ph.D. degrees awarded till date, based on research conducted in the institute. The laboratory at present has a sanctioned strength of 62 scientists, 65 technical and 54 administrative staff. About 150 JRF/SRF are pursuing their doctoral work and an equal number of project assistants are involved in contract research activities. The Institute receives about Rs.25 crores of budgetary support per annum.

3. Previous Studies

Several investigators have conducted bibliometric analysis of research productivity of different countries in the world. Many such bibliometric and scientometric studies have been carried out in India too. These studies have helped in identifying India's publications growth rate which has been relatively much faster in recent years.

Sudhier and Priyalakshmi³ highlighted the research productivity of scientists of the ICAR-Central Tuber Crops Research Institute (CTCRI), Thiruvananthapuram, for the period 2000-2010, by analysing bibliographic details of 1076 research articles obtained from the annual reports of CTCRI. Suma and Sudhier⁴ studied 137 Ph. D theses submitted by the scientists of CSIR- National Institute for Interdisciplinary Science & Technology (NIIST) during 2001-2010 and found that majority of the theses (107) were in Chemistry. 1521 papers of NIIST were included in the 124 theses out a total of 137 dissertations studied. Singhai⁵ examined Gujarat Cancer & Research Institute (GCRI) scientists' performance based on their publications during 1975-2010 drawn from Pubmed database.

Kaushik⁶ identified various bibliometric aspects of the scientific contributions of the researchers and faculty of National Dairy Research Institute (NDRI), Karnal published during 2001-2011. The average number of authors per contribution was 3.61 and degree of collaboration 0.98. Jeysankar, Ramesh Babu and Rajendran⁷ analysed bibliographical details of 1282 research articles published by the scientists of CECRI during the period 2000-2009. It was found that 2009 was the most productive year with 194 articles and collaborative research was dominant with the highest degree of collaboration being 0.98 in the year 2005.

Sudhier and Abhila⁸ analyzed the research productivity of social scientists at the Centre for Development Studies (CDS), Thiruvananthapuram, during 1998-2008. There were 599 research papers published during the period, including 38.23% journal articles and 15.03% working papers. More than 66% journal articles were

published in Indian Journals and EPW contributes the highest number of articles (34.50%). Sahu, Goswami and Choudhary⁹ analysed R & D publication growth, its characteristics with reference to the National Metallurgical Laboratory, an R & D institution under CSIR, based on data obtained from the Science Citation Indices. It was found that the highest number of 120 papers was published by the laboratory in the year 2010, out of which 28 papers received 62 citations during the same period. The average number of publications per year was 88.1 and the average citation per paper was 5.02.

Bhatia¹⁰ analyzed quantitatively the research publications published by the scientists of National Institute of Occupational Health (ICMR) Ahmedabad, India during 2002 -2006. Upadhye et al.¹¹ analysed the publications of Nuclear Physics Division at BARC, Bombay. There were 257 research papers published during 2003-2008 in diverse domains of Nuclear Physics. Sudhier¹² in his scientometric study analysed the publications of physics researchers at the Indian Institute of Science (IISc), Bangalore. There were 267 papers published during 1999-2003 and the highest number of papers was in the year 2001.

Several studies have been reported in the area of scientometrics on institutional productivity, particularly in the Indian context and a few of them are: Maheswaran, Kumar and Sridharan¹³ conducted a study based on the research publications generated by Structural Engineering Research Centre (SERC) during the years 2002-2006. A bibliometric study of research publication trend among scientists of Central Potato Research was studied by Sharma¹⁴. Bala and Gupta¹⁵ studied growth and impact of research output of Govt. Medical College and Hospital, Chandigarh. Kumbar, Gupta and Dhawan¹⁶ described the growth, contribution and impact of research carried out by the scientists of University of Mysore in S & T. Mukherjee¹⁷ analyzed the authorship pattern of scientific productions of the four most productive Indian academic institutions for the eight year period from 2000 to 2007. Sevukan and Sharma¹⁸ in their bibliometric analysis, studied the research output of biotechnology faculties in some Indian central universities.

Jeevan and Sen¹⁹ conducted a study based on the journal publications generated by the Inter University Accelerator Centre, and the Accelerator Group at the Tata Institute of Fundamental Research (TIFR) during 1997-1999. Dhawan and Gupta²⁰ studied the institutional performance, based on publications output of Indian Physics research. Scientometric analysis of 1044 papers published

by the scientists of Radiochemistry division at Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC) during 1958-2005 in diverse domains were conducted by Kademani et al.²¹

Angadi et al.²² in the Tata Institute of Social Sciences during 2001-2004, Kademani et al.²³ in the Analytical Chemistry Division of BARC during 1972-2003, Kademani et al.²⁴ in the Bio-Organic division of BARC, Mehta²⁵ in the National Chemical Laboratory (NCL), Pune, Gopikuttan²⁶ in the Science Departments, Faculty of Science, University of Kerala during 1980-1999, Jeevan and Gupta²⁷ in the IIT, Kharagpur, Gupta et al.²⁸ in the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research (CSIR) and Garg and Rao²⁹ in the Indian Physics Laboratory, New Delhi.

From the studies it is evident that there has not been a proper study carried out to determine the research output of the scientists of NIIST, one of the prestigious laboratories of CSIR. Hence this study is undertaken.

4. Objectives

The major objectives of the study are:

- To study the publication pattern of NIIST research publications
- To examine the authorship pattern.
- To identify the most productive author
- To determine the degree of collaboration and co-authorship index.
- To identify the preferred journals for publication.
- To prepare a rank list of publishers.

5. Methodology and Sample Data

For the study, 1080 journal articles were considered, out of the total of 1190 publications. The bibliographic details of all the publications have been collected from the NIIST's official website and the collected data was analysed using Microsoft Excel software. In this study, data are analyzed on the basis of bibliometric techniques - type of documents, most productive authors, authorship pattern and core journals of NIIST scientists.

6. Analysis and Discussion

6.1 Trend of NIIST's Research Output

Table 1 shows the year-wise quantitative distribution of literature under study during the period 2007-2011.

Table 1. Trend of NIIST’s research output

Sl. No	Year	Journal Articles	Patents	Total	Percentage
1	2007	233	14	247	21
2	2008	242	41	283	24
3	2009	207	24	231	19
4	2010	200	20	220	18
5	2011	198	11	209	18
Total		1080	110	1190	100.00

The analysis shows that the research output of NIIST during 2007 to 2011. The highest output is in 2008 with 283 (24%) and lowest in 2011 with 209 (18%) over the five year period. During the period 110 patents were filed by the NIIST scientists.

Figure 1 it is clear that 2008 is the most productive year as far as the journals and patents filed are considered.

6.2 Length of Contributions

A study on the number of pages per publication was carried out and the same is tabulated in Table 2.

It has been found that almost 90% of the articles are published with less than 10 pages. Of this, half of the papers are below 5 pages and the remaining are in the range of 5- 10 pages. More than 20 pages are very negligible with just 0.45%.

6.3 Authorship Pattern

Figure 2 it is evident that only one percentage of the authors could publish articles of their own. All others are dependent on one or more than one authors to have their articles published. Overall the trend is uniform from two authors upwards up to five authors plus. The reduction in single author articles gives an indication that most of the articles are published in collaboration with a mentor. Also it gives an indication that most of the articles are published by junior research fellows. It can be inferred from this result that team effort in research has become integral part of NIIST researchers.

6.4 Most Prolific Authors

Table 3 depicts a list of most prolific authors who have produced more than 6 papers during the period of study.

Table 3 it is evident that only one author, G. Vijay Nair has published 32 Papers. The number of publications of

Figure 1. Trend of NIIST’s research output.

Table 2. Length of contributions

Sl. No.	Range	No. of Papers	Percentage
1	1 to 5	490	45
2	6 to 10	489	45
3	11 to 15	81	8
4	16 to 20	15	1
5	More than 20	5	0.45
Total		1080	99.45

Figure 2. Authorship Pattern.

Vijay Nair is more than double of the next highest scorer S. Vinu, who has 15 papers in his credit. M. Sundarajan and P. Shanmugham with 14 and 12 publications each come in the next positions respectively.

6.5 Degree of Collaboration

Authorship trend and collaborative research are important facets of bibliometric studies. The authorship pattern, one of the prime aspects of citation analysis mainly deals with the kind of authors, nature and degree of collabo-

Table 3. Most productive authors

Sl. No.	Name of Author	No. of Papers	Rank
1	Vijay Nair, G	32	1
2	Vinu, S	15	2
3	Sundararajan, M	14	3
4	Shanmugam, P	12	4
5	Anjana, P. S	11	5
6	Dastager, S. G	11	5
7	Subodh, G	11	5
8	Biju, A	10	6
9	Sarun, P. M	10	6
10	Vinod, K	10	6
11	Anas, S	9	7
12	Anisha, G. S	9	7
13	Rojan P John	9	7
14	Baiju, K. V	8	8
15	Rajan, T. P. D	8	8
16	Anil Kumar, P	7	9
17	Mangalaraja, R. V	7	9
18	Nisha, P	7	9
19	Shabna, R	7	9
20	Simi, C. K	7	9
21	Sreekumar, V. M	7	9
22	Sudha, J. D	7	9

ration among them and collaborative trend of authors. Collaboration and team work are among the most important necessities of scientific and technological work today.

Subramanyam³⁰ proposed a mathematical formula for calculating author's degree of collaboration in a discipline. The degree of collaboration among authors is the ratio of the number of multi-authored papers published to the total number of papers published in a discipline during certain period of time. The degree of collaboration (collaboration coefficient) among authors is measured mathematically as:

$$C = \frac{N_m}{N_m + N_s}$$

Where, C = degree of collaboration

N_m = number of multi authored papers

N_s = number of single authored papers

The degree of collaboration in different years is calculated as per the above equation and is presented in the Table 4.

The degree of collaboration over the years is calculated and it varies from 0.970 to 0.995. The mean value

Table 4. Degree of collaboration

Year	Single authored articles	Multi authored articles	Degree of Collaboration	Total
2007	7	226	0.970	233
2008	3	239	0.988	242
2009	1	206	0.995	207
2010	1	199	0.995	200
2011	3	195	0.985	198
Total	15	1065	0.986 (mean)	1080

is found to be 0.986. The single v/s multi authored papers are also seen in the Table 4 with their percentage of contributions. During the period of study it is found that 995 of the total journal articles are multi-authored and only 1% of the papers are single authored. The study revealed that team research is prevalent in the NIIST.

6.6 Pattern of Co-Authorship Index (CAI)

The co- authorship index formula suggested by Garg and Padhi³¹ is used to examine how the pattern of CAI has changed during the period of study.

$$CAI = \left\{ \frac{(N_{ij} / N_{io})}{(N_{oj} / N_{oo})} \right\} \times 100$$

N_{ij} = Number of papers having j authors in block i

N_{io} = Total output of block i

N_{oj} = Number of papers having j authors for all blocks

N_{oo} = Total number of papers for all authors and all blocks

$J = 1, 2, 3 \dots n$

For calculating the CAI the entire data are divided in to three blocks as single author, two authors and more than two author publications. The analysis of the results of the co- authorship index is given in the Table 5.

A study of the co-authorship pattern gives an indication of the individual's ability to publish a paper individually or in collaboration with a mentor or co-researcher. Overall it has been found that the single author papers are relatively much lesser than multi authored papers. It is observed from the analysis that the value of CAI for two authored papers is the highest and single authored papers is the lowest, which indicates that the collaborative research is increasing among the NIIST scientists.

6.7 Year-wise Distribution of Journal Articles

The distribution of journal articles during the period of study is shown in the Table 6.

Table 5. Pattern of Co-Authorship Index

Year	Single author	CAI	Two authors	CAI	More than 2 authors	CAI	Total
2007	7	216.34	44	106.24	182	96.65	233
2008	3	89.28	49	113.93	190	97.16	242
2009	1	34.78	26	70.65	180	107.57	207
2010	1	35.98	39	109.73	160	99.01	200
2011	3	109.09	34	96.6	161	100.61	198
Total	15		192		873		1080

Table 6. Year-wise distribution of Journal articles

Year	Articles in Foreign Journals	Articles in Indian Journals	Total
2007	221	12	233
2008	227	15	242
2009	201	6	207
2010	195	5	200
2011	183	15	198
Total	1027	53	1080
Total in %	95.00	5.00	100.00

Table 6, it is found that the growth rate of publications is almost stagnant and there is no improvement in the publication in journals. Rather it could be found there is a very marginal decrease in the journal publication trend. From the analysis it is clear that NIIST scientists prefer to publish in foreign journals (95%) and very few papers are published in Indian journals (5%). The relative contribution in Indian journals is significantly lower when compared to foreign journals.

6.8 Preferred Journals by the NIIST Scientists

Journals are the formal primary medium of communication for researchers. The cycle of information consumption, transmission and production is complex. Journals alone cannot represent all phases of the cycle. Nevertheless, the role of journals in information gathering, use and transmission by researchers cannot be over estimated. The interactions of NIIST researchers with journals in terms of publishing papers are examined in this study.

The NIIST’s research contributions, which has been published as journal articles appeared in 325 national

and international journals. A list of top ranked journals is given in the Table 7 according to the number of articles they published.

On the basis of analysis it is found that there are 25 journals which have published 10 or more papers during the period of study. These journals can be considered as the most productive journals. It is found that Journal of Alloys and Compounds by Elsevier and Journal of the American Ceramic Society by Wiley Blackwell topped the list with 40 publications each. The same is followed by Bio resource Technology and Applied Surface Science both by Elsevier with 29 and 23 publications respectively. However it can be seen that the impact factors of the top two journals are relatively low at 1.51 and 2.10. Of the top 25 journals only 5 of them have impact factor more than 5. *Angewandte Chemie International Ed* has the maximum impact factor with 10.87 and 10 articles published in the same journal. Also it has been found in the top 25 list, none of the journals are Indian. Of the top 25, seven of them are journals published by Elsevier. It is interesting to see that there is no journal from India in the top ranked list.

6.9 Distribution of Papers by Geographical Distribution

The 325 journals used by NIIST scientists to publish their works are published from 32 countries. The journals are analysed according to their country of origin and same is tabulated in Table 8.

It has been found that USA is the top ranked country with 101 journals, followed by England and Netherlands with 67 and 44 journals. It is also important to note that NIIS scientists publish their research papers in 23 journals and it is 4th in the list.

Table 7. Preferred journals by the NIIST scientists

Sl. No	Name of Journals	Publisher	Country	IF	No. of articles	Rank
1	Journal of Alloys and Compounds	Elsevier	Switzerland	1.51	40	1
2	Journal of the American Ceramic Society	Wiley Blackwell	USA	2.101	40	1
3	Bio resource Technology	Elsevier	England	4.453	29	2
4	Applied Surface Science	Elsevier	Netherlands	1.576	23	3
5	Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology	Humana Press	USA	1.04	22	4
6	Tetrahedron Letters	Elsevier	England	2.538	20	5
7	Journal of Physical Chemistry B	Amer. Chemical Society	USA	4.189	19	6
8	Organic Letters	Amer. Chemical Society	USA	5.128	19	6
9	International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology	Springer	England	0.743	18	7
10	Chemical Communications	Royal Soc Chemistry	England	5.34	17	8
11	Food Technology and Biotechnology	Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology	Croatia	1.273	16	9
12	Materials Letters	Elsevier	Netherlands	1.748	16	9
13	Journal of Sol-Gel Science and Technology	Springer	USA	1.433	15	10
14	Tetrahedron	Elsevier	England	2.897	14	11
15	Journal of Applied Polymer Science	Wiley Blackwell	USA	1.187	13	12
16	Synthesis - Stuttgart	Georg Thieme Verlag Kg	Germany	2.47	13	12
17	Journal of Applied Physics	Amer. Inst. Physics	USA	2.201	12	13
18	Materials Research Bulletin	Elsevier	USA	1.812	12	13
19	Chemistry of Materials	Amer. Chemical Society	USA	5.046	11	14
20	Journal of Polymer Science Part A - Polymer Chemistry	Wiley Blackwell	USA	3.821	11	14
21	Journal of the American Chemical Society	Amer. Chemical Society	USA	8.091	11	14
22	Superconductor Science & Technology	IOP Publishing Ltd	England	1.847	11	14
23	Angewandte Chemie International Ed	Wiley Blackwell	Germany	10.879	10	15
24	Inorganic Chemistry	Amer. Chemical Society	USA	4.147	10	15
25	Journal of Materials Science - Materials in Electronics	Springer	Netherlands	1.054	10	15

Table 8. Geographical distribution of journals

Sl. No	Country	No. of Journals	Rank
1	USA	101	1
2	England	67	2
3	Netherlands	44	3
4	Germany	23	4
5	India	23	4
6	Switzerland	13	5
7	Japan	8	6
8	Brazil	3	7
9	Hungary	3	7
10	Singapore	3	7
11	Australia	2	8
12	France	2	8
13	Iran	2	8
14	China	2	8

Table 9. Frequency-wise analysis of journals

Sl. No	Frequency/ Yr.	Count	Rank
1	12	99	1
2	24	41	2
3	6	39	3
4	4	35	4
5	8	10	5
6	26	10	5
7	18	8	6
8	52	8	6
9	16	7	7
10	10	5	8
11	11	4	9
12	20	4	9
13	48	4	9
14	9	3	10
15	51	3	10

6.10 Frequency-wise Analysis of Journals

A study was carried out on the number of publications per year of the journals and the analysis is tabulated in Table 9.

It has been found that the monthly journals (12/yr) are more preferred by the scientists for publishing their papers and it accounts for 99 journals followed by semi-monthly journals (24/yr) with a share of 41 journals. Bi-monthlies (6/yr) and quarterlies (4/yr) are the other types of journals preferred for publication (39 and 35 respectively). It is also found that regular publishers with one journal per month or fortnight had an edge over the other journals. Irregular publishers are not preferred among scientists for publications.

6.11 Rank List of Publishers

In order to identify the leading publishers of journals, an analysis has been made for the ranking of publishers. The results of the analysis of the leading publishers are shown in the Table 10.

The study found that Elsevier is the leading publisher among the NIIST scientists with the coverage of 102 journals and Springer with 33 journals comes second. The study revealed that, as far as NIIST scientists are concerned, NISCAIR (CSIR) is the leading publisher from India with 5 journals.

Table 10. Rank list of publishers

Sl. No	Name of Publisher	No. of Journals
1	Elsevier	102
2	Springer	33
3	Wiley - Blackwell	24
4	ACS	20
5	Wiley - VCH	12
6	Taylor & Francis	11
7	Royal Society of Chemistry	10
8	IOP Publishers	05
9	NISCAIR	05

7. Conclusion

The study quantitatively identifies 1190 publications of NIIST (CSIR) researchers for the five year period, 2007-2011. It has been found that only 4.91% of the papers are published in Indian journals. Most of the publications are made in world-class journals which gives an indication on the quality of the publications. It is also found that single author papers constitute only 1% of the total published papers. Among the scientists, G. Vijay Nair is the most productive contributor with 32 papers.

On the basis of the study, further scientometric indicators can be accessed to gain a clear understanding of the strength and deficiency of scientific activity of NIIST

researchers. The quantitative study on the productivity of the scientists of the NIIST provides some insight into the dynamics of research activity and it will enable the policy makers of the CSIR and science administrators to make available adequate facilities in the areas of their research.

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